

ORGANIZATION OF NURSING CARE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article examines the organization of nursing care to the population of Uzbekistan in the context of modern challenges and prospects for the development of healthcare in the country. The article discusses the history of the development of the nursing service, modern methods of organizing and training medical personnel, as well as current challenges and prospects for the further development of this area. The authors emphasize the importance of the role of nurses in providing quality medical care to the population and offer recommendations for improving working conditions, improving the qualifications and expanding the competencies of medical personnel in Uzbekistan.

Key words: nurse, population, organization, healthcare, medical care, patient, documentation.

Nurses in Uzbekistan play a key role in providing quality medical care to the population. They perform a wide range of duties, including: Patient care: Nurses provide care to patients in hospitals, clinics, and at home. This includes performing medical procedures, wound care, taking vital signs, preparing for medical procedures, and more. Nurses perform various medical procedures such as injections, infusions, drawing blood for testing, changing dressings, etc. Nurses assist doctors in conducting examinations, diagnosing and treating patients, and preparing for surgeries. Conducting preventive activities: Nurses participate in the implementation of vaccinations, screening programs, disease prevention consultations and other activities to promote public health. They maintain medical

records, including completing medical records, patient reports, and procedures performed.

Nurses in Uzbekistan receive education and specialized training to effectively perform their duties. Their work is an integral part of the country's healthcare system and plays an important role in providing care and support to patients.

The history of the development of the nursing service in Uzbekistan dates back decades of constant development and improvement. Beginning in the early years of Soviet rule, the country established health care and medical care systems in which nurses played a key role. During the Soviet era, active work was carried out to educate and train medical personnel, including nurses, to provide the population with quality medical care. Nurses performed a variety of roles, ranging from caring for patients in hospitals and clinics to carrying out preventive activities in rural areas. After gaining independence in 1991, Uzbekistan continued to improve its healthcare system and the training of medical personnel, including nurses. New training standards were developed, modern work methods were introduced, and working conditions and remuneration for medical workers were improved. Today, nurses in Uzbekistan continue to play an important role in ensuring the population's access to quality medical care. At the same time, as part of the country's healthcare development strategy, they actively participate in the process of introducing innovative approaches and technologies, and also continue to improve their professional level through constant training and exchange of experience with colleagues from other countries. The organization of nursing care for the population of Uzbekistan is based on an integrated approach to ensuring the availability of quality medical care for all citizens of the country. Within this organization:

1. **Medical institutions:** There are public and private medical institutions in the country, including hospitals, clinics, maternity hospitals, outpatient clinics and pharmacies. Nurses provide a wide range of health care services, from initial patient visits to procedures and rehabilitation.

2. Specialized programs: National health programs carry out specialized activities aimed at improving the health of the population. Nurses are actively involved in these programs, including vaccinations, screening for various diseases and providing preventive counseling.
3. Education and training of medical personnel: There are educational institutions in the country that train future medical workers, including nurses. In addition to educational programs, refresher courses and internships are conducted for current medical professionals to update their knowledge and skills.
4. Information support: Patients receive information about available medical services, operating hours of medical institutions and contact information of specialists through various information channels, including the Internet and mobile applications.

In general, the organization of nursing care to the population in Uzbekistan is focused on providing a high level of medical care and maintaining the health of the country's citizens. Challenges and prospects for the further development of nursing care in Uzbekistan are closely related to general trends in the development of healthcare and society:

1. Lack of personnel: One of the main challenges is the lack of qualified health workers, including nurses. This requires efforts to increase the number of medical schools, make the profession more attractive and improve working conditions.
2. Providing quality education: It is important to ensure a high standard of nursing education, including modern teaching methods, up-to-date curricula, and access to simulation training.
3. Integration of new technologies: The implementation of modern technologies in healthcare, such as electronic health records and telemedicine, requires training of healthcare personnel, including nurses, to effectively use these tools.

4. Expansion of competencies: Given the changing needs of health care and the increase in chronic diseases, nurses must develop their competencies in the areas of chronic care, palliative care and the provision of psychosocial support.
5. Improving working conditions: Providing opportunities for professional growth, social protection and satisfactory wages will help attract and retain highly qualified nurses.

Prospects include more efficient use of resources through optimization of medical processes, improved access to medical services for the population, and the development of specialized areas in nursing practice. Increasing the status and attractiveness of the nursing profession also helps attract and retain talented professionals in the field. Modern methods of organizing and training medical personnel in Uzbekistan include the use of modern technologies and techniques adapted to the medical field.

-Use of simulation training: Doctors and nurses gain hands-on experience using simulation simulators and equipment to learn how to respond to a variety of medical scenarios without putting patients at risk.

- Online education and e-resources: Many educational materials and courses are available online, making training easier to access and increasing flexibility for medical personnel, especially in remote areas.

- Multimedia teaching methods: The use of videos, audio recordings and interactive materials helps to visualize and absorb information more effectively.

- Active learning methods: Group discussions, case studies and role-playing games contribute to the development of analytical and communication skills of medical staff.

- Professional development and retraining: A system of continuous training and professional development helps healthcare workers stay up to date with the latest medical advances and technologies. These methods help ensure that medical

personnel in Uzbekistan are highly trained and prepared to respond effectively to a variety of medical challenges and situations.

Conclusion. In the context of a rapidly changing medical environment and the ever-growing needs of the population of Uzbekistan, the organization of nursing care plays a key role in providing quality and affordable medical care. Although there are challenges such as staff shortages, improving working conditions and the introduction of new technologies, the country continues to move forward, developing and improving its medical system. Nurses in Uzbekistan play an important role in providing care and support to patients, their professionalism and dedication help maintain the health and well-being of the population. Further development of the nursing service requires joint efforts by government, educational institutions and medical organizations to improve training, expand competencies and raise the status of the nursing profession. This will allow the country to effectively cope with the challenges of modern healthcare and provide quality medical care to all citizens of Uzbekistan.

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